

Bridging ocean observing across the SoCal Bight

Workshop report

SCCWRP & CalCOFI Workshop
Feb 19, 2026
9am - 4:30pm
In person, SCCWRP, Costa Mesa, CA

Executive Summary

Main takeaways

- *Two programs, one complementary picture.* SCCWRP and CalCOFI together span the full Southern California Bight. SCCWRP's inshore and benthic coverage through the Bight Program and CalCOFI's offshore time series and quarterly cruises, but have yet to systematically combine their data. Merging these datasets could answer regional-scale questions that neither program can address independently, and the workshop identified several concrete ideas ready to pursue.
- *The collaboration is well-timed given state policy priorities.* Ocean acidification, the 30x30 biodiversity mandate, rapid response, and microplastics are all active state priorities, and California still lacks a coordinated ocean monitoring program to address them. With over 100 siloed monitoring programs operating across the state, the SCCWRP–CalCOFI partnership represents a practical and timely path toward the kind of integrated, regional science that can inform policy, with joint proposals as the near-term mechanism for turning workshop momentum into funded, durable work.
- *Rapid response: we have the data and experience, but need a formal plan.* Both programs have relevant datasets and prior coordination experience, but no formal trigger protocol exists to activate a joint rapid response for acute events such as wildfires, oil spills, and floods, as well as slower-moving crises like harmful

algal blooms. Defining a clear threshold that initiates a structured CalCOFI–SCCWRP response plan was identified as a practical and achievable near-term step, in coordination with SCCOOS, the IOOS Regional Association serving Southern California.

- *Ocean acidification & hypoxia: chemistry and biology need to be measured together.* The biggest opportunity exists between continuous chemical monitoring and episodic biological sampling. The group's central priority was to establish sentinel sites. At these sites, chemistry data from fixed platforms (moorings and shore stations) would be paired with ship-based eDNA and organismal observations, complemented by glider surveys and validated against ROMS-BEC output.
- *eDNA: method standardization will help to compare data.* The two programs are closely aligned in approach but use different filter types and protocols, leaving taxonomic gaps in the middle of the trophic spectrum. A ~\$50K method optimization study comparing pore sizes and analytical approaches would clarify what each program is missing and lay the groundwork for a shared, standardized sampling framework.
- *Microplastics: combining methods and archives will help to reveal a more holistic picture.* SCCWRP brings large-scale benthic monitoring and high-confidence analytical methods. CalCOFI brings surface water sampling via manta tows and a substantial sample archive. Intercalibrating the two programs' methods and applying them to CalCOFI's archived samples could unlock long-term trend data that neither program's single-cycle snapshot can yet provide.

Action items

Near-term

- Overlay SCCWRP and CalCOFI sampling footprints to identify spatial overlap and gaps across all four focal areas (eDNA, OAH, microplastics, rapid response).
- Inventory existing sample backlogs (especially archived CalCOFI manta trawl and eDNA samples) with documentation of collection methods and stations.
- Begin exchanging samples between programs and initiate joint writing on shared datasets, including pulling CalCOFI data to validate SCCWRP's ROMS-BEC model output.
- Conduct a ~\$50K eDNA method optimization study comparing pore sizes and depths (ddPCR + metabarcoding) to identify taxonomic gaps across both programs' current approaches.

- Conduct a historical reanalysis of CalCOFI and Bight biological and chemical observations alongside ROMS-BEC model output, focusing on cross-shore OAH gradients where the two programs' coverage is most complementary.
- Match SCCWRP benthic trawl data with CalCOFI larval fish records to link inshore recruitment to adult offshore spawning biomass.

Medium-term

- Develop and submit joint proposals
- Pursue targeted eDNA species assay development (e.g., krill, pteropods, squid, sharks, lobster phyllosoma; estimated at about \$250–500K).
- Define a formal emergency response trigger protocol establishing clear thresholds that activate a coordinated CalCOFI–SCCWRP–SCCOOS response plan for acute events (e.g., wildfires, oil spills, HABs).
- Intercalibrate microplastics analytical methods between SCCWRP and Deheyne Lab at SIO, and apply methods to CalCOFI's archived manta trawl samples to unlock long-term trend data.

Longer-term

- Establish integrated sentinel monitoring sites combining continuous chemical measurements from moorings and shore stations with periodic biological sampling and glider surveys to bridge the observational gap between the very nearshore and more offshore regimes.
- Establish a long-term shared sample repository (ideally hosted at SIO), archiving eDNA filters and extracted DNA from monitoring programs throughout California to enable retrospective analyses as methods evolve.
- Pursue a \$5M, 5–10 year integrated biodiversity and ecosystem dynamics assessment, beginning with a 0–3 year baseline study, and a ~\$1M quantitative fish community assessment using metabarcoding and molecular bait hybridization.

Ongoing

- Reconvene in approximately six months (with taxonomic and glider representatives added) to assess progress and advance joint proposals.
- Continue engagement with legislative staff and decision-makers to communicate monitoring gaps and the value of program integration, and identify three to five high-impact state priorities to pursue with philanthropic and federal funding.

Overview

The Southern California Coastal Water Research Project (SCCWRP) and the California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations (CalCOFI) share many objectives and a long history of partnership in the Southern California Bight. Additionally, both programs are increasingly working on related questions around monitoring, sampling, and emerging tools. The SCCWRP & CalCOFI workshop brought together 27 SCCWRP- and CalCOFI-affiliated scientists and staff (Appendix 1), along with others involved in coordinating monitoring and observing efforts in the region to: 1) *build and strengthen relationships between SCCWRP and CalCOFI* and 2) *identify and further develop areas of alignment and focused collaboration on specific topics of mutual interest, including environmental DNA (eDNA), ocean acidification & hypoxia (OAH), rapid response monitoring, and microplastics*. The day consisted of presentations, breakout groups, and discussion sessions (Appendix 2).

Introduction

Steve Weisberg, SCCWRP Director, opened the meeting by framing it as a working session aimed at having initial, opening conversations. SCCWRP and CalCOFI are two complementary organizations with shared interests in water quality, biodiversity, and climate impacts across the Southern California Bight, with a history of collaboration between the two organizations. The central question for the day was how the two organizations could better coordinate their monitoring efforts across analytical methods, sampling design, and joint research outputs. For example, bringing together SCCWRP's inshore and CalCOFI's offshore oxygen data was highlighted as a concrete example where merging datasets could provide a more holistic picture of oxygen in the Southern California Bight.

Mark Gold, CalCOFI Director at Scripps Institution of Oceanography, followed by emphasizing the opportunity to think creatively about what the two organizations could accomplish together. He situated the collaboration within a broader state policy landscape, noting that ocean acidification and hypoxia, biodiversity monitoring under the 30x30 mandate, rapid response to events like the LA wildfires and HABs, and microplastics are all designated state priorities. He also highlighted that California still lacks a comprehensive, coordinated ocean monitoring program and the siloed nature of over 100 existing monitoring programs in California is both a challenge and an opportunity.

The day's discussions were organized around four focal areas, ocean acidification and hypoxia (OAH), eDNA, rapid response, and microplastics monitoring, as concrete starting points where SCCWRP and CalCOFI could begin building something more integrated together. The goal was to get specific about what each program samples, how those samples are collected and analyzed, and where and when coordination makes the most sense. Ultimately, with an eye toward identifying concrete opportunities for collaboration and laying the groundwork for joint efforts and proposals that would lead to stronger science across the SoCal Bight.

SCCWRP & CalCOFI: Overviews & partnership

Overview of CalCOFI

Noelle Bowlin, CalCOFI Director at NOAA Southwest Fisheries Science Center, opened with a brief history of CalCOFI and overview of existing efforts around the focal areas (eDNA, OAH, and emerging issues).

CalCOFI is a multi-institution program with a sampling footprint stretching from Baja California to the Oregon-California border. CalCOFI traces its origins to landing tax revenue that funded what would become one of the longest-running marine monitoring efforts in the world. The program conducts quarterly cruises: winter and spring surveys extend into a broader domain to capture the spawning range of sardine and anchovy, while summer and fall cruises focus on the core area. This grid has been sampled consistently for over 40 years, and for the past 21 years the program has also maintained nearshore stations. The domain and frequency of sampling have evolved over the decades, supported by new technology and expanded partnerships, with a growing emphasis on making data publicly accessible.

On ocean acidification and hypoxia, dissolved inorganic carbon samples have been collected since 1983, with a gap from 2001 to 2008. Since resuming, the program has added underway water sampling for pH and pCO₂, and CTD-mounted pH sensors, now six years into that record. A backlog of unprocessed samples remains an active challenge.

CalCOFI has several eDNA efforts. First, the NOAA CalCOFI Ocean Genomics program (NCOG) has collected bacteria and phytoplankton from CTD bottle water since 2014. More recently, underway large-volume sampling targeting fish and marine mammal eDNA began in 2023, and analysis of ethanol-preserved bongo net samples dating to the late 1990s began in 2024. The consistency and contemporaneous nature of sampling across these efforts, combined with rigorous curation and archiving, is what gives the dataset its long-term value.

Several emergent issues have drawn the program in new directions. DDT contamination in vertically migrating forage fish, first documented by John McGregor in 1972, has resurfaced through mesopelagic bycatch in current samples. The January 2025 Palisades Fire prompted sampling through the event and 20 days of mesocosm experiments examining the ecological impacts of ash and debris entering the ocean. Microplastics work began in the early 2000s in collaboration with Mark Ohman's lab and NOAA, and the recent anchovy boom has raised new questions about food chain dynamics. The long-running archive holds significant untapped potential to address questions the program has not yet formally investigated.

Looking ahead, priorities include processing a 12–15 year backlog of manta trawl samples relevant to both fish monitoring and microplastics research, improving data management so datasets can be more readily matched and shared with partners, and expanding glider-based sampling to augment ship surveys. A glider equipped with a shadowgraph camera was deployed alongside the spring 2026 CalCOFI cruise in March. Gallo et al. 2022 was cited as a model for what coordinated regional monitoring can produce when programs work together effectively.

In closing, CalCOFI was described as California's greatest insurance policy. The archive is vast, the time series is long, and the data hold answers to questions the state is only now beginning to ask. What's needed is the funding to actually extract those answers.

Q&A: What does CalCOFI underway sampling entail?

The vessel draws water from 3–5 meters depth through a coated mesh intake filter. For eDNA samples enriched for metazoan organisms, water is sampled continuously over the course of a transect by directly running the underway outflow through a 5-micron filter to capture larger particles and cells, which improves metazoan eDNA yield by excluding many of the tiny bacterial cells. Volume filtered is recorded throughout. Separately from eDNA, the Continuous Underway Fish Egg Sampler (CUFES)

allows the team to identify which fish species are actively spawning at sea, particularly useful for anchovy and sardine.

Overview of SCCWRP

Ken Schiff, SCCWRP Deputy Director, framed his presentation around the opportunity of bringing together the two largest and longest-running regional marine monitoring programs in Southern California, and offered the Bight Program as a model for what coordinated, integrated monitoring can look like at scale.

SCCWRP has a long history of facilitating regional monitoring programs spanning oceans, streams, beaches, stormwater, and marine protected areas, and currently supports 14–15 active regional programs including ocean acidification and hypoxia, eDNA, and fire response. The Bight Program is the organization's flagship ocean monitoring effort, launched in 1994, operating on five-year cycles, and now recognized as a national model for coordinated, integrated regional monitoring.

The core logic of the Bight model is straightforward: rather than having a single agency attempt to answer regional-scale questions on its own, SCCWRP brings together over 100 monitoring agencies, spanning industry, local government, consultants, academics, and nonprofits, each contributing a small number of sites or measurements that together yield tens of thousands of sample analyses across thousands of square miles. A key enabler is a regulatory tradeoff in which agencies are permitted to substitute participation in the Bight Program for some of their routine local discharge monitoring requirements. This grassroots structure has proven durable: what began in the 1970s as just SCCWRP has grown to roughly 150 participating entities as of the 2023 cycle.

SCCWRP's role is as facilitator, helping to define the right monitoring questions and clarifying what managers will actually do with the answers, designing efficient sampling frameworks,

ensuring QA/QC so that data from dozens of agencies can be meaningfully combined, managing and publicly distributing the resulting datasets, and translating findings into actionable information for water quality managers.

Three examples were used to illustrate where the Bight Program has driven

concrete management impact. On beach water quality, the early monitoring concentrated on known problem areas, which gave an incomplete regional picture.

Bight data demonstrated that Southern California beaches are generally safe during dry weather, meeting water quality objectives 97% of the time between Memorial Day and Labor Day across more than 275,000 sample analyses per year, but that wet weather conditions are where water quality deteriorates significantly, with all beaches effectively behaving like storm drains after rainfall. Those findings shaped the Clean Beach Initiative, focused regulatory attention on storm drain management, and established the beach-mile-days framework the state now uses to assess and communicate beach water quality. Sediment quality objectives and trash and microplastics monitoring provided two additional examples of Bight data underpinning regulations, supporting impaired waters listings and delistings, and directly informing state policy decisions.

The current Bight '23 cycle includes eight elements, sediment quality, trash and microplastics, water quality and ocean acidification and hypoxia, estuaries, harmful algal blooms, and bioaccumulation, and the open question posed to the group was how the Bight Program and CalCOFI, as the two largest and longest-running regional monitoring programs in Southern California, could work together to influence management and regulatory decisions in ways neither could accomplish independently.

Q & A: What is the spatial footprint, sampling parameters, and contributors of the SCCWRP Bight Program sampling efforts?

The Bight Program samples from the head of tide, including estuaries, out to the offshore basin at depths of up to 1,000 meters, with the Channel Islands as the effective offshore boundary. The sampling design captures estuaries, the shoreline, the continental shelf, and the water column above, including inputs from storm drains measured at the source, at the ocean interface, along the beach, and up the water column.

On a question related to the parameters, county health departments focus on fecal indicator bacteria (e.g., *E. coli* and *Enterococcus*) but the program also looks at microbes more specifically associated with human feces, which represent the highest public health risk. A question about physical sample archiving noted that current practice is to retain samples for about five years, with relatively little long-term archiving. The point was raised that as monitoring

questions continue to evolve, there is a stronger case for archiving more, particularly given that DNA-based samples collected for public health purposes could be relatively easily retained and repurposed for broader ecological questions down the line.

On participation, military installations and power generating stations are active contributors (e.g., the U.S. Navy, U.S. Marine Corps, and various dischargers) all participate alongside the broader regulated community. This is a meaningful feature of the model: regulated parties have compliance obligations and a strong interest in ensuring their data meet a high quality standard, which aligns well with SCCWRP's QA/QC goals. Ensuring consistent quality across 12–14 boats collecting samples simultaneously requires substantial investment in training and education, bringing all participants up to a common standard for both field and lab analysis so that quality tends to persist across the five-year cycle once established. Between surveys, ongoing local monitoring programs serve as a venue for introducing and beta-testing new methods across the full range of natural variation and human impact gradients before transferring them more broadly to participating agencies.

Topic areas: Rapid response, OAH, eDNA, microplastics

The rest of the day focused on topical breakout groups that align with areas of overlap for SCCWRP and CalCOFI. These included rapid response, OAH, eDNA, microplastics.

Rapid response – Alvina Mehinto, SCCWRP & Rasmus Swalethorp, CalCOFI

The discussion approached rapid response broadly, encompassing acute events such as wildfires, oil spills, and floods, as well as slower-moving crises like harmful algal blooms. The central theme was how CalCOFI, SCCWRP, and the Southern California Coastal Ocean Observing System (SCCOOS) datasets, collected independently over many years, could be better leveraged together both to establish baselines and to mount coordinated responses when events occur. Rapid response coordination among CalCOFI, SCCWRP, and SCCOOS isn't new, as work on wildfire and oil spill impacts along the coast dates back nearly 15 years. The programs aren't starting from scratch, and together they can leverage resources and infrastructure for a far stronger and broader response.

Three areas of near-term collaboration emerged. The first was quantifying the relative loading of pollutants from runoff versus atmospheric deposition, a question relevant to wildfire response in particular. SCCOOS, CalCOFI, SCCWRP, and NCSU and NASA datasets all contain relevant parameters, though merging them will require internal analysis to align and clean the data. The second was combining historical fish larvae and trawl data to track recruitment dynamics. CalCOFI holds larval fish and water column data while SCCWRP and its member agencies have trawl records, sediment chemistry, and tissue data. Merging and integrating the datasets for species

assessed by the different programs (e.g., sand dab, sole, turbot, vermillion rockfish) could provide valuable recruitment information for fisheries managers. The third topic discussed was microlayer sampling. The Bight and CalCOFI programs are currently measuring the surface water layer using different methods and capturing different parameters. Given that the surface microlayer concentrates pollutants and is ecologically significant for fish larvae, there is a clear opportunity to standardize and harmonize sampling procedures and analyze a common suite of parameters across both programs. This would expand the range analysis that each program is currently conducting and further explore the relationship between water column contaminants and fish health.

Other project ideas were identified as longer-term opportunities requiring more coordination and resources. These included matching water samples with sediment and black carbon data, aligning Santa Ana wind records with fire events, emergency deployment of a floating Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) to assess fire impacts on plankton biomass and HAB species and toxins, and adding manta trawls to both programs to build a shared baseline dataset for microplastics and fish. An observation was raised that ash aggregates at the ocean surface in the same features where zooplankton concentrate, potentially increasing exposure, and that archived zooplankton and ichthyoplankton samples may already hold relevant toxics data worth examining.

The group discussed the need to develop a benchmark that would trigger a formal rapid response action plan. Although the discussion was framed around Southern California and the three core programs, the group recognized that coordination should eventually expand to include additional agencies

Ocean Acidification & Hypoxia (OAH) – Martha Sutula, SCCWRP & Christina Frieder, SCCWRP & Anya Stajner, CalCOFI

A central theme of the OAH discussion was the mismatch in sampling frequency and coverage between observing platforms. Moorings and gliders now can provide continuous or near-continuous measurements of key physical and select chemical parameters (e.g., temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and in some cases pCO₂/pH), while many other chemical variables (such as nutrients and full carbonate system measurements) and most biological observations remain episodic and ship-based. The group explored how to better couple these data streams. For example, by establishing sentinel sites where moorings anchor high-frequency physical and chemical measurements, and periodic ship-based sampling adds paired eDNA, abundance, and organismal data. Emerging technologies (e.g., IFCBs and other fixed or autonomous biological sensors) are beginning to narrow this gap by enabling higher-frequency biological observations.

A gap also exists in the cross-shore sampling to detect and understand cross-shore gradients and learn how the nearshore and offshore affect each other. Gliders emerged as a critical tool for bridging this gap, particularly for filling in

cross-shore variability and vertical habitat compression between mooring locations and ship sampling sites. Two gliders were discussed: one running continuously on nearshore CalCOFI lines with mini-moorings as the nearshore endpoint, and a second equipped with a pH sensor. The group noted that while gliders are effective at characterizing vertical habitat structure, they do not directly capture organism responses, which reinforces the need to pair glider surveys and moorings with biological sampling. The idea of running gliders combined with moorings through model predictions, using ROMS-BEC output to generate testable hypotheses and then checking those predictions with field data and biology, was identified as a concrete near-term opportunity. Lines 80 and 90 were highlighted as priority locations given existing assets including moorings, pier stations, gliders, and mini-moorings. An analysis suggested there are approximately 11 locations where a climate trend is detectable based on existing data.

On the chemistry side, the group noted that the Alin et al. algorithm relating measurable parameters to carbonate chemistry can be updated. Updating this relationship, potentially through improvements to the ESPER model, was flagged as relatively accessible low-hanging fruit. The amount of samples that can be collected and analyzed remains a limiting factor, making it important to think carefully about where glider lines are deployed and what questions they are designed to answer. Connecting inshore mooring records with offshore glider sampling was seen as a way to extend the value of both.

On the biological side, euphausiids were discussed as strong indicators of El Niño and PDO cycles, with a reasonable hypothesis that subtropical euphausiid species with low oxygen tolerance may serve as indicators of low oxygen events, though disentangling OAH signals from broader climate variability would require substantial work. Crustaceans were raised as another candidate taxa for linking pCO₂ and oxygen exposure to population-level responses, with questions about how robustly the metabolic index translates to real-world populations. Pteropod-specific eDNA assays and probability of detection consistency across programs were also discussed, along with shell dissolution methods, with SEM versus micro-CT identified as a methodology comparison worth pursuing. *Limacina helicina* was initially noted as a strong coastwide indicator species, but its absence in SCCWRP samples and relatively low abundance in CalCOFI samples suggests it may not be well suited as an indicator species. The group therefore recommended exploring other more cosmopolitan holoplanktonic shelled gastropods as indicator species.

Three priority areas were identified for follow-up. The first and most immediately actionable was a historical reanalysis of CalCOFI and Bight biological and chemical observations alongside ROMS-BEC model output, with emphasis on cross-shore gradients, capitalizing on SCCWRP's nearshore coverage and CalCOFI's offshore time series, with glider data incorporated as it becomes available. This would also include

updating the Alin et al. equations to produce a shared set of algorithms to be used by both programs. Estimated costs on the CalCOFI side alone were noted at \$500,000 or more. The second was methodology improvement, finding faster, cheaper, and more reliable approaches to key measurements and identifying additional indicator species sensitive to OAH gradients across the Bight. The third, more resource-intensive priority was developing new coupled chemical and biological sampling approaches: linking biological sampling to mooring infrastructure that POTWs have already been investing in, optimizing sampling designs around glider surveys to illuminate chemistry-biology relationships, and ultimately configuring the combined CalCOFI, Bight, and SCCOOS monitoring effort to detect early warning signals of climate change and eutrophication at locations most likely to show a detectable trend. Additionally, monitoring should be increased during late summer (August–September) and in areas of peak habitat compression identified through ROMS-BEC model outputs, where low aragonite saturation and hypoxia are most likely. The group also emphasized the value of expanding glider-based measurements of pH and dissolved oxygen to improve both temporal and spatial coverage.

eDNA – Susie Theroux, SCCWRP & Nastassia Patin, CalCOFI

The Bight and CalCOFI eDNA sampling programs are closely aligned in their approaches, though knowledge gaps remain around taxonomic coverage and there is a clear need and opportunity for method standardization across both programs. The groups share a broad range of research interests, including fish and invertebrate populations (e.g., squid), ocean acidification indicator taxa, phytoplankton and HABs, zooplankton, microbes, and multitrophic relationships.

CalCOFI's eDNA sampling spans multiple platforms and target taxa. The NCOG program (since 2014) conducts CTD-based discrete sampling at five depths using 0.22 micron Sterivex filters, primarily targeting microbes. Attempts to amplify fish and cetacean markers from these samples have had limited success. The MOSAIC program (since 2023) targets surface vertebrate eDNA using large-volume underway sampling through 5 micron filters, with a planned transition to hourly sampling for improved spatial resolution. Zooplankton have been sampled via ethanol-preserved bongo tows since 1996, with 0.2 micron filtration of 100ml subsamples from concentrated jars. Accessing the concentrated net tow samples is highly valuable because krill detection from Niskin bottles remains difficult. Marine mammal detection efforts using the d-loop marker gene have successfully detected both common (e.g., delphinids) and rarer cetacean taxa using eDNA, complementing visual and acoustic survey efforts and often providing improved taxonomic resolution. In sum, CalCOFI has strong coverage at the microbial and cetacean ends of the trophic spectrum, but the middle ground remains an open

opportunity. Efforts to expand and standardize sampling are ongoing, including testing of two automated underway instruments this year, CSIRO's Quokka and MBARI's FIDO, as well as a spring 2026 collaboration with Prof. Rob Knight's lab (UC San Diego) to collect paired microbiome, metabolome, and metaproteome data. A longer-term aspiration is a single eDNA sample capable of capturing all trophic levels, though this is considered ambitious given tradeoffs in filter pore size, water volume, and the risk of bacterial sequences swamping metazoan diversity.

The Bight program's eDNA sampling began in late 2024, using 0.45 micron PES filters with a vacuum pump system selected for its practicality on small vessels, offering low contamination risk, gravity filtration, and the ability to process multiple samples simultaneously. Following feedback that earlier approaches were too technical and generated excess plastic waste, the program shifted toward a simpler, streamlined workflow using self-desiccating filters. Water samples are collected at the surface, DCM, and depth, with 1–2 L single replicates at monthly cruises and three 1 L replicates at two depths quarterly. Since 2018, plankton tow net samples have been preserved for molecular analyses (200 micron bongo, preserved in RNeasy (Bight 2018 survey) or ethanol (Bight 2023 survey)). Currently, Bight partners are exploring the use of AI and imaging tools to augment or replace traditional benthic trawls for fish populations. Regulatory drivers originally focused on toxins and tumors in fish tissue and a fish index of biological integrity developed by SCCWRP in the 1970s, but there is growing interest in whether more integrative approaches, including microbial indicators that correlate with ecosystem health and fish community composition, could provide a more sensitive and comprehensive assessment framework.

The Bight program is primarily driven by water quality monitoring needs through SCCWRP, while CalCOFI is oriented around fisheries and broader oceanographic science. A key challenge for applying eDNA to fisheries is the lack of a quantitative component, which is now being addressed through multiple emerging approaches. These include ddPCR assays for indicator species (e.g., sardine and anchovy), exploration of molecular bait hybridization for semi-quantitative targeted detection across a broad range of taxa, and the development of quantitative metabarcoding approaches for estimating relative or absolute abundance across diverse communities. CDFW represents an important potential user, particularly for state-managed species outside the federal council process and eDNA methods applied through CalCOFI sampling platforms could offer a much-needed source of fisheries-independent relative abundance data.

Near-term key actions

Method Optimization Study (~\$50K) A comparative study examining three pore sizes across two depths, combined with ddPCR and metabarcoding, to assess adequacy of current approaches for inventorying all priority taxonomic groups, essentially identifying who we are missing.

Targeted Species Assays (\$250–\$500K) Building on the 2025 OAH & eDNA Workshop, the first step would be assembling a priority species list, followed by development of ddPCR assays for fish and ocean acidification species of interest. Target taxa under consideration include krill, pteropods, squid, sharks, and lobster phyllosoma.

Longer-term goals

Integrated Biodiversity Assessments and Ecosystem Dynamics (~\$5M) A 5–10 year effort encompassing responses to environmental change and trophic interactions, beginning with a 0–3 year baseline study.

Quantitative Fish Community Assessment (~\$1M) Approaches under consideration include metabarcoding combined with qPCR or UMIs, and molecular bait hybridization for semi-quantitative targeted detection.

RNA Studies for Fish Life Stage Identification Over a 5–10 year horizon, RNA-based approaches could be used to pull out developmental marker genes and identify life stage, informing recruitment dynamics and population assessments.

Capacity development to bridge near- and long-term goals

Near-term actions can directly enable longer-term goals with investment in two key infrastructure areas:

- Automated Sampling Instrumentation, to increase throughput, reduce user error, and accelerate sample accumulation.
- Long-Term Shared Sample Repository, ideally state-supported and physically hosted at SIO, archiving filters and/or extracted DNA to enable retrospective analyses.

The inability to reliably extract and analyze eDNA from formalin-preserved samples also remains a key gap, which would unlock decades of archived material (e.g., manta trawl collections). Advancing methods in this area would substantially expand the temporal reach of eDNA applications. In parallel, there is strong potential for integrating eDNA with traditional microscopy workflows, using molecular data to guide or streamline identification and thereby reduce the overall microscopy burden while preserving taxonomic resolution and validation.

Additionally, the group discussed the potential to screen for ecological functions (e.g., plastic degradation, calcification) alongside biodiversity. This is currently most tractable for microbes, where known gene targets exist for biogeochemical functions. Extending functional screening to eukaryotes remains more challenging but possible at the family level. The broader framing, coupling what organisms do with what they are, was seen as a valuable direction for integrating eDNA biodiversity data with ecosystem function assessments.

Microplastics – Leah Thornton Hampton, SCCWRP & Dimitri Deheyn, SIO-UCSD

While CalCOFI does not currently conduct microplastics monitoring, the Bight program is currently performing a special study to quantify and characterize microplastics in sediment and mussels across the region. A major challenge for the Bight program is that current analytical methods, while high-confidence, are laborious, time-consuming, and expensive. For these reasons, sample analyses are limited to larger microplastic particles (i.e., 125 μm and greater). In parallel, Dimitri Deheyn's lab at Scripps Institution of Oceanography, is developing faster, cheaper approaches capable of detecting smaller particle sizes. This provides a great opportunity for method comparison and intercalibration between the two programs to demonstrate that their approaches are complementary and may be used in parallel to fill knowledge gaps, particularly for smaller classes of microplastics.

The Bight program is currently more benthic in focus, while CalCOFI's MANTA tows offer a surface water perspective, with future addition of MANTA tows to the Bight program potentially bridging that gap. Applying methods to analyze microplastics in the hundreds of archived CalCOFI samples could unlock long-term trends data that the Bight's single-year snapshot cannot yet provide. Expanding and sustaining microplastics monitoring across both programs would create a more comprehensive understanding of microplastic distribution in coastal and offshore habitats throughout central and southern California. This approach could help identify contamination hotspots, evaluate potential sources, and determine whether these patterns persist or vary across seasons and years.

Near-term priorities include inventorying existing sample backlogs with clear documentation of what was collected, at what stations, and by what methods, and developing a more detailed spatial overlap map of CalCOFI and SCCWRP stations to assess sampling comparability, an approach that could also be extended to larval fish and benthic trawl datasets.

Conclusion & Next steps

Steve Weisberg reflected on what success looks like at different timescales. In the near term, a key measure is simply whether people have met, built relationships, and feel comfortable reaching out to one another directly. Some immediate next steps are already in motion, including beginning to write papers together, exchanging samples to keep momentum going, and pulling CalCOFI data to validate SCCWRP-developed ROMS-BEC model output. Over the medium term, the group identified joint proposal writing as a next step, with the OPC OAH call flagged as a potential near-term funding opportunity, and follow-up meetings to advance shared work. Longer-term success will be measured by whether 5-year plans and joint proposals actually materialize from the relationships and ideas seeded at this workshop. To sustain momentum, the group

discussed reconvening in a half year, potentially with additional participants (e.g., taxonomic and glider representatives).

A few outstanding items include overlaying SCCWRP and CalCOFI sampling footprints, matching SCCWRP benthic trawl data with CalCOFI larval fish data to develop indices linking recruitment to adult spawning biomass, and exploring overlap between larval fish and pelagic invertebrate data collected alongside CTD casts, with the potential to align SCCWRP trawl data with CalCOFI larval fish datasets where their geographic coverage overlaps. This pairing is particularly valuable because CalCOFI currently lacks strong inshore recruitment data and much of the recruitment signal for species like anchovy occurs closer to shore than CalCOFI typically samples, whereas SCCWRP's benthic trawls capture that inshore signal.

Additionally, there is opportunity to explore data comparability between SCCWRP discharger monitoring and CalCOFI at shared or nearby stations (including CTD, larval fish, trawl, and eDNA data). Examining how both datasets responded during the marine heat wave could also reveal whether local-scale shifts observed by SCCWRP mirror the broader patterns seen in CalCOFI data. Archiving of SCCWRP eDNA and genetic samples was also raised as an important step to enable future data integration. On the policy side, the group noted that there is value in continuing to engage with legislative staffers and decision makers, helping them understand monitoring gaps and how integration across established monitoring programs could be done effectively. The broader priority is identifying three to five high-impact state priorities that could attract support from philanthropy and federal sources to fill those gaps. The workshop highlighted shared opportunities, facilitated discussion and idea generation, and set the stage for enhanced collaboration between SCCWRP and CalCOFI.

Suggested citation

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Appendix 1. List of participants

Name	
Steve Weisberg	SCCWRP

Ken Schiff	SCCWRP
Leah Thorton Hampton	SCCWRP
Dimitri Deheyn	SIO-UCSD
Eric Stein	SCCWRP
Uwe Send	CalCOFI
Erin Satterthwaite	CalCOFI
Noelle Bowlin	CalCOFI
Andrew Thompson	CalCOFI
Ed Weber	CalCOFI
Mark Ohman	CalCOFI
Alvina Mehinto	SCCWRP
Rasmus Swalethorp	CalCOFI
Susie Theroux	SCCWRP
Nastassia Patin	CalCOFI
Julia Coates	CalCOFI
Ryan Guillemette	SCCWRP
Jeff Bowman	CalCOFI
Zack Gold	PMEL
Martha Sutula	SCCWRP
Anya Stajner	CalCOFI
Todd Martz	CalCOFI
Christina Frieder	SCCWRP
Jayme Smith	SCCWRP
Faycal Kessouri	SCCWRP
Mark Gold	CalCOFI
Clarissa Anderson	SCCOOS

Appendix 2. Agenda

9:45 – 10:00 | Welcome & opening – Steve Weisberg, SCCWRP & Mark Gold, CalCOFI

Goal: Set shared context and purpose for the day

Activity: Brief framing of SCCWRP–CalCOFI partnership, shared objectives, and focus areas

Outcomes:

Shared understanding of why we're here

Clear goals and expectations for the working meeting

10:00 – 10:55 | SCCWRP & CalCOFI: Overviews & partnership – Noelle Bowlin, CalCOFI & Ken Schiff, SCCWRP

Goal: Establish a common understand of each program and partnership

Activity: Program overviews and facilitated discussion

Outcomes:

Shared understanding of current CalCOFI & SCCWRP monitoring efforts

Identification of overlaps, gaps, and opportunities for alignment

Initial ideas for what a more coordinated SoCal Bight monitoring approach could look like

10:55 – 11:00 | Break

11:00 – 12:00 | Breakout discussions: idea generation - Erin Satterthwaite, CalCOFI

Goal: Identify high-value opportunities for collaboration

Activity: Small-group discussions guided by key questions

Outcomes:

Short list of priority ideas for joint work

Initial recommendations on what we should be doing together

Clear candidates for follow-on implementation discussions

3 Breakout Group Discussions

Emergency response – *Alvina Mehinto, SCCWRP & Rasmus Swalethorp, CalCOFI*

OAH – *Martha Sutula, SCCWRP & Christina Frieder, SCCWRP & Anya Stajner, CalCOFI*

eDNA – *Susie Theroux, SCCWRP & Nastassia Patin, CalCOFI*

12:00 – 1:00 | Lunch

please continue conversations over lunch & optional SCCWRP tour

1:00 – 2:15 | Breakout discussions: implementation strategy - Erin Satterthwaite, CalCOFI

Goal: Move from ideas to action

Activity: Small-group planning focused on feasibility and coordination

Outcomes:

- Practical approaches for implementation
- Identify “early wins” and proposal-ready ideas
- Preliminary thoughts on staffing, coordination, and funding needs

3 Breakout Group Discussions

Emergency response – *Alvina Mehinto, SCCWRP & Rasmus Swalethorp, CalCOFI*

OAH – *Martha Sutula, SCCWRP & Christina Frieder, SCCWRP & Anya Stajner, CalCOFI*

eDNA – *Susie Theroux, SCCWRP & Nastassia Patin, CalCOFI*

2:15 – 3:15 | Report-outs & integrated group discussion - Erin Satterthwaite, CalCOFI

Goal: Build shared priorities across topics

Activity: Group report-outs and full-group discussion

Outcomes:

- Agreement on priority areas to move forward
- Shared understanding of cross-topic linkages
- Clarify the key decisions needed to advance collaboration

3 - 5 mins each with 15 min each for Q & A

Emergency response – *Alvina Mehinto, SCCWRP & Rasmus Swalethorp, CalCOFI*

OAH – *Martha Sutula, SCCWRP & Christina Frieder, SCCWRP & Anya Stajner, CalCOFI*

eDNA – *Susie Theroux, SCCWRP & Nastassia Patin, CalCOFI*

3:15 – 3:45 | Break

3:45 – 4:30 | Next steps & wrap-up – Steve Weisberg, SCCWRP & Mark Gold, CalCOFI

Goal: Establish follow up beyond the meeting

Activity: Whole-group discussion on follow-up actions

Outcomes:

- Agreed-upon next steps and near-term timeline
- Decision on whether and how to reconvene